

Personality Traits and Study Skills among Junior High School Social Studies Students: Basis for Intervention Program

Jay R. Baliar ✉
Holy Cross of Davao College, Philippines

Article History:

Received: 20.04.2025 Revised: 05.05.2025 Accepted: 15.05.2025 Published: 16.05.2025

Abstract

The study investigates the relationship between personality traits and study skills among Junior High School Social Studies students. Utilizing a quantitative correlational research design, data were gathered from 150 randomly selected students across five public high schools. The study employed adapted survey questionnaires based on the Big Five Personality Model and established study skills assessments to evaluate personality traits—specifically openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and sensitivity—and study skills, which included time management, concentration, information processing, reading comprehension, and test strategies. Results revealed a significant moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.55813$, $p = 0.0001$) between personality traits and study skills, indicating that students who exhibit strong personality traits tend to develop effective study habits. However, regression analysis showed that personality traits accounted for only 31.17% of the variance in study skills, suggesting the influence of additional external factors such as learning environment, instructional quality, and social support systems. In response to these findings, the study proposes the Personality-Driven Study Skills Enhancement Program (PDSSEP), aimed at aligning students' study strategies with their personality profiles to foster improved academic performance. The study concludes that personality traits play a key role in shaping study skills but emphasizes the importance of holistic interventions addressing other contributing factors. Further research is recommended to explore these additional influences to develop comprehensive academic support programs.

Keywords: *personality traits, study skills, Big Five Model, correlation, academic performance.*

Suggested citation: Baliar, J.R. (2025). Personality Traits and Study Skills among Junior High School Social Studies Students: Basis for Intervention Program. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(3), 176-182. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(3\).16](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(3).16)

Introduction

Dealing with inadequate study skills continues to be a daunting task for many students because recent research shows it contributes to academic difficulties in terms of time management, self-persuasion, and procrastination. In one study, a combination of poor time and effort management skills coupled with low academic self-efficacy was found to correlate with engagement in procrastination behaviors,

leading to poorer performance for students (Jeffords et al., 2018). A study in 2023 again showed that cognitive and social learning factors, such as collaboration with peers or teacher guidance, are of importance to enhance academic performance for students, indicating the complexity around slide-issues (McKenna, 2023). Moreover, students' psychological flexibility has been suggested to strongly relate with their ability of dealing effectively and reducing avoidance behavior against academic

challenges (Psychreg & Relajo-Howell, 2023). These findings suggest that the low level of student skills in terms of their studies is a concern for students and parents, which can be better addressed by combining individual efforts with collective learning practices.

Poor study skills are a global issue, and different countries have pointed this out in their various educational contexts. For instance, in the Philippines, recent reports and studies indicate that a large percentage of university students struggle with study habits, which also leads to low academic performance (Quinco, 2013). Research has identified prevalent weaknesses in how students are effectively prepared for the transition to higher education, with recognized poor study strategies resulting in challenges of self-directed learning (Van Zelst, n.d.). Thus, South Africa is also facing problems with time management and critical thinking aspects among school students especially at high schools (Mayet, 2017). These stories give a picture of how widely the issue is spread among nations and educational systems.

Failure to resolve the problem of poor study skills may result in serious academic repercussions such as lower performance, higher dropout rates and lasting difficulties upon employment at work (Jeffords et al., 2018; Nkosi, 2023). Poor study habits of some students are the core reason why certain students perform poorly than others in school (Kassaw & Demareva, 2023). Yet, there seems to be a lack of literature that notably scrutinizes appropriate interventions capable or designed on the basis of addressing root causes behind study skills inefficiency, especially in diverse cultural backgrounds such as the Philippine setting (PNU, 2022; Hutchinson & Kettlewell, 2015). Identifying effective strategies to enhance study skills and their impact on outcomes is critical for educational policy and practice as it has broad implications in preparing students not only academically but holistically in their journey of lifelong learning. Bridging these gaps can allow for enhanced support structures and help to close the education divide worldwide.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the significance of personality traits as determinant of study skills. Specifically, it pursued the following objectives:

1. To determine the levels of Personality traits of Junior High School students in terms of openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and sensitivity: and study skills of Junior High School students in terms of time management and attitude, concentration and memory, organizing and processing information, writing and reading comprehension, and test strategies and test anxiety.
2. To determine the significant relationship between the personality traits and study skills of Junior High School students
3. To determine the significance of the degree of influence of personality traits on study skills of Junior High School students.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study is based on the Big Five Personality Model (Fiske, 1949), which classifies personality into five broad traits: Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Sensitivity. These traits influence individual differences in behavior and learning. Specifically, the behaviors and learnings included in this study are time management, concentration and memory, organizing and processing information, writing and reading comprehension, and test strategies and test anxiety (UHCL Counseling Services, 2001).

The independent variable in this study is the personality trait with five indicators: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and sensitivity. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the study skills with four indicators: time management and attitude, concentration and memory, organizing and processing information, writing and reading comprehension, and test strategies and test anxiety.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative correlational research design to examine the relationship between personality traits and study skills among

Junior High School students. Conducted in five selected public high schools in Digos City, the study utilized statistical techniques to analyze the strength and direction of correlations without establishing causation. A simple random sampling method was used to ensure fair selection, with a total of 180 respondents—30 for a reliability test and 150 for correlation analysis—ensuring a diverse and representative sample.

Data collection was carried out using two adapted survey questionnaires. The Personality Traits questionnaire, based on the Big-Five Trait Taxonomy by John and Srivastava (1999), assessed openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism using a 4-point Likert scale. Meanwhile, the Study Skills questionnaire, adapted from UHCL Counseling Services (2001), evaluated students' study habits, focusing on areas such as time management, concentration, and self-regulated learning. These tools provided valuable insights into the connection between personality traits and academic study behaviors.

The study strictly followed ethical research guidelines, ensuring confidentiality, informed consent, and compliance with institutional research ethics standards. Measures were taken to protect respondent privacy and uphold data integrity, strengthening the reliability of the study. By providing insights into how personality traits influence study skills, the research contributes to the development of educational programs that enhance students' academic performance. The findings are expected to support the Department of Education, teachers, and students in refining instructional strategies and study skill development initiatives.

Results

The study analyzed the relationship between personality traits and study skills among Junior High School students using descriptive, correlation, and regression analyses. The findings showed that students generally exhibited high levels of both personality traits and study skills, with Openness and Extraversion being the most dominant traits and Time Management being the strongest study skill. Correlation analysis revealed a moderate

positive relationship between personality traits and study skills, while regression analysis indicated that personality traits accounted for 31.17% of the variance in study skills, suggesting that other factors also play a role in academic performance.

Based on these findings, the study proposed the "Personality-Driven Study Skills Enhancement Program (PDSSEP)" to help students develop effective study habits based on their personality traits. The four-year program includes self-awareness training, skill development, integration into academic routines, and mastery through mentorship, with activities such as peer mentoring, stress management techniques, and teacher workshops. The program aims to foster self-discipline, motivation, and collaborative learning to enhance students' study strategies and academic performance.

To support the implementation of PDSSEP, a structured budget plan was developed, with funding sourced from school funds, DepEd grants, private sponsorships, and PTA contributions. The program also includes a monitoring and evaluation framework through quarterly assessments, student feedback, and teacher reports to track progress and refine interventions. Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of integrating personality-based approaches into education to enhance students' study skills and overall learning experiences.

Discussions

The study emphasizes the significant role personality traits play in shaping students' study skills and academic success. The findings reveal that Junior High School students exhibit high levels of key personality traits such as Openness, Conscientiousness, and Extraversion, which contribute to their ability to engage in effective learning strategies (Deveci & Ersen, 2022). High Openness fosters curiosity and innovation in learning, while Conscientiousness enhances organizational skills and diligence, both of which are essential for academic achievement. Additionally, students who exhibit high levels of Extraversion benefit from collaborative and dynamic learning environments, reinforcing the idea that personality traits influence how

individuals interact with academic tasks (Sumardi, 2023).

In addition to personality traits, the study skills of the respondents were also rated high, indicating that students generally possess well-developed learning strategies that support academic performance. Effective time management, concentration, and test-taking strategies were found to be strong among the participants, aligning with previous studies that emphasize the importance of these skills in achieving academic success (Nwankwo & Egbunike, 2021). Time management skills, in particular, were linked to reduced procrastination and improved academic performance, suggesting that students who can effectively plan and allocate their study time tend to perform better academically (Rafique et al., 2021). Furthermore, strong organizational skills and the ability to process information efficiently were found to be crucial in helping students manage their workload and retain information effectively (Credé & Phillips, 2016).

The correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between personality traits and study skills. This suggests that students with stronger personality traits, particularly in Conscientiousness and Openness, tend to develop more effective study habits, which ultimately contribute to their academic success (Dalvi-Esfahani et al., 2021). The findings support previous research that highlights the role of personality in shaping students' approach to studying, reinforcing the need for tailored learning strategies based on personality differences (Kovach, 2018). By understanding how personality traits influence study habits, educators and students can adopt more effective learning techniques that align with individual strengths and weaknesses (Bouiri et al., 2021).

The regression analysis indicated that personality traits account for 31.17% of the variance in study skills, suggesting that while personality plays a role in learning, other factors also contribute significantly. External influences such as the learning environment, instructional quality, peer interactions, and motivation may play a greater role in shaping students' study skills than

inherent personality traits alone (Fitzsimons & Finkel, 2018). This finding underscores the complexity of academic achievement, highlighting the need to consider multiple factors when developing educational interventions. While personality traits provide a foundation for learning behaviors, structured educational programs and support systems can further enhance students' academic skills and overall performance (Foote et al., 2023).

One explanation for the remaining 68.83% variance in study skills could be the role of environmental and situational influences, such as the quality of teaching, availability of academic resources, and family support (Awujo et al., 2022). These factors may have a more immediate and measurable impact on students' study habits, as opposed to personality traits, which tend to develop over time. Additionally, study skills are often learned behaviors that can be enhanced through targeted educational interventions, such as study skills training, mentorship programs, and structured academic support (Ma et al., n.d.). This suggests that regardless of personality traits, students can improve their study habits through guided learning experiences and practice.

The study also implies that educators should adopt a more comprehensive approach when designing learning interventions, rather than focusing solely on personality traits. While personality traits can provide insights into students' learning preferences, they should not be the only basis for determining study strategies. Instead, a combination of personality-based learning techniques and structured skill-building activities can offer a more effective approach to academic success (Kokkinos et al., 2024). This aligns with previous research that suggests integrating both personality-driven and environmental factors in educational planning can lead to more effective student outcomes.

Furthermore, the findings highlight the need for differentiated instruction strategies that cater to diverse personality profiles. For instance, structured study routines may be more beneficial for conscientious students, while interactive and discussion-based learning strategies may better suit students high in Extraversion and Openness (Bakar & Herng, 2018). Educators should also

consider incorporating mentorship programs and peer collaboration initiatives that allow students to develop study habits that align with their personality traits and learning styles. By leveraging students' strengths and addressing their weaknesses, teachers can create a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

While personality traits play a crucial role in shaping students' study habits, they are only one of many factors influencing academic success. A well-rounded approach that combines personality-based learning strategies with structured educational interventions can lead to more effective learning outcomes. Schools should focus on fostering both intrinsic and extrinsic factors that contribute to study skills development, ensuring that students receive comprehensive support for academic success. Further research should explore additional variables that impact study skills, such as motivation, socio-economic background, and institutional support, to provide a more holistic understanding of the factors influencing student learning.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that personality traits indicated by Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Sensitivity are significant determinant of study skills by 31.17% influence. This conclusion affirms the Big Five Personality Model stating that indicators of Personality Traits significantly influence individual behavior and learning.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, it is recommended that further research be conducted to explore additional variables influencing study skills beyond personality traits, as 68.83% of the variance remains unexplained. Educational institutions should implement activities that foster personality development, helping students enhance traits such as Conscientiousness and Openness, which contribute to academic success. Teachers are encouraged to adopt differentiated instruction strategies tailored to students' personality traits, ensuring that learning experiences are

personalized and effective. Additionally, training programs should be designed to equip educators with the skills needed to support diverse personality profiles, promoting inclusivity in teaching practices. Schools should also strengthen guidance and counseling services, helping students understand how their personality traits influence their study habits and academic performance. Finally, community-based initiatives such as mentorship programs and peer collaboration activities should be established to support holistic student development and enhance their study skills through structured and engaging experiences.

References

- Awujo, N. C., Aremu, D. O., Kenneth, E. P., Imarenezor, E. O. A., & Aremu, S. O. (2022). Microbial contamination of the bread samples sold in Nigeria. *Human, Health & Halal Metrics*, 3(2).
- Bakar, Z. A., & Heng, T. C. (2018). Relationships between personality traits and academic achievement among primary school students in Johor, Malaysia. *Advanced Science Letters*, 24(5), 3512–3515. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2018.11425>
- Bouiri, O., Lotfi, S., & Talbi, M. (2021). Correlative study between personality traits, student mental skills and educational outcomes. *Education Sciences*, 11(4), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040153>
- Counseling and Mental Health Center | University of Houston-Clear Lake. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.uhcl.edu/cmhc/>
- Credé, M., & Phillips, L. A. (2017). Revisiting the power pose effect. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 8(5), 493–499. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550617714584>
- Dalvi-Esfahani, M., Niknafs, A., Alaedini, Z., Ahmadabadi, H. B., Kuss, D. J., & Ramayah, T. (2021). Social media addiction and empathy: Moderating impact of personality traits among high school students. *Telematics and Informatics*, 57, 101516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2020.101516>
- Deveci, C. A., & Ersen, R. K. (2022). Predictors of academic achievement at different levels of

- socioeconomic status. *International Education Studies*, 15(3), 39. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v15n3p39>
- Fitzsimons, G. M., & Finkel, E. J. (2018). Transactive-goal-dynamics theory: A discipline-wide perspective. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 27(5), 332–338. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721417754199>
- Foote, A., Gooyabadi, M., & Addleman, N. (2023). Factors in learning dynamics influencing relative strengths of strategies in poker simulation. *Games*, 14(6), 73. <https://doi.org/10.3390/g14060073>
- Hutchinson, J., & Kettlewell, K. (2015). Education to employment: Complicated transitions in a changing world. *Educational Research*, 57(2), 113–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2015.1030848>
- Jeffords, J. R., Bayly, B. L., Bumpus, M. F., & Hill, L. G. (2018). Investigating the relationship between university students' psychological flexibility and college self-efficacy. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 22(2), 351–372. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1521025117751071>
- John, O. P., & Srivastava, S. (1999). The Big-Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and theoretical perspectives.
- Kassaw, C., & Demareva, V. (2023). Determinants of academic achievement among higher education students found in low-resource settings: A systematic review. *PLoS ONE*, 18(11), e0294585. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0294585>
- Kokkinos, C. M., Antoniadou, N., & Voulgaridou, I. (2024). Majors unleashed: Unraveling students' personality profiles across academic disciplines. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-024-05721-2>
- Kovach, M. (2018). A review of classical motivation theories. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in Education*, 7(1), 34–53. <https://doi.org/10.32674/jise.v7i1.1059>
- Ma, J., Hogan, M. J., Eyre, E. L. J., Lander, N., Barnett, L. M., & Duncan, M. J. (2021). Enhancing the implementation and sustainability of fundamental movement skill interventions in the UK and Ireland: Lessons from collective intelligence engagement with stakeholders. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-021-01214-8>
- Mayet, R. (2017). Supporting at-risk learners at a comprehensive university in South Africa. *Journal of Student Affairs in Africa*, 4(2), 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.14426/jsaa.v4i2.1527>
- McKenna, L. (2023, February 10). Why studying is so hard, and what teachers can do to help. *Edutopia*. Retrieved from <https://www.edutopia.org/article/why-studying-is-so-hard-and-what-teachers-can-do-to-help>
- Nwankwo, C. A., & Egbunike, N. S. (2021). Effect of time management training on academic task procrastination of secondary school students in Onitsha Local Government Area of Anambra State. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5136739>
- Psychreg, & Relajo-Howell, D. (2023, January 30). Well-being matters: But how can we enhance well-being across the academic community? *Psychreg*. Retrieved from <https://www.psychreg.org/well-being-matters-how-can-we-enhance-well-being-across-academic-community/>
- Quinco-Cadosales, M. (2013). The study skills of first-year education students and their academic performance. *LAMURE International Journal of Education*, 6(1).
- Rafique, A., Khan, M. S., Jamal, M. H., Tasadduq, M., Rustam, F., Lee, E., Washington, P. B., & Ashraf, I. (2021). Integrating learning analytics and collaborative learning for improving student's academic performance. *IEEE Access*, 9, 167812–167826. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2021.3135309>
- Shrout, P. E., & Fiske, S. T. (2014). Personality research, methods, and theory. In *Psychology Press eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315806815>
- Sumardi, S. (2023). The influence of student management on students' attitudes and behavior

in learning at school. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 6(7).
<https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v6-i7-16>

Van Zelst, C. (n.d.). A correlational study of social skills, problem behaviors, and academic

competence among first-grade students. *Rowan Digital Works*. Retrieved from
https://rdw.rowan.edu/etd/1755/?utm_source=rdw.rowan.edu%2Fetd%2F1755&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages